

lines that showed resistance in the first test were screened again. For the 9 that still showed resistance, insect preference and the number of eggs laid on leaves of

each rice line were recorded. Resistant Colombo and Rathu Heenati and susceptible TN1 were used as controls. Lines with high resistance scores had

fewer eggs and fewer insects than susceptible TN1. IR5853-198-1-Mr-3-2 had fewest eggs and insects. □

Reaction of rice varieties to gall midge in Tamil Nadu

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Gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) is a destructive pest of rice in Tamil Nadu, particularly Madurai, Tanjore, and Trichi districts. Sep infestations cause 25 to 30% yield loss.

From Aug to Dec 1981, 46 prerelease and released varieties from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad, were field-screened at Thaniamangalam, Madurai. Each variety was grown in a single 3-m-long row in 3 replications. GM infestation was encouraged by growing TN1 on borders, cutting tillers, keeping water in the plots to attract flies, and lighting plots at night. Total number of hills infested were recorded (see table). Six varieties were not infested (see table). □

Field screening of rice varieties for gall midge resistance, Madurai, Tamil Nadu, 1981.^a

Variety	Hills infested ^b (%)	Variety	Hills infested ^b (%)
IET6056	45.8 a	IET7329	16.4 bcdefghij
IR20	41.7 ab	Eswarakora	15.2 bcdefghij
Chitraikar	36.3 abc	W1263	14.1 bcdefghij
TN1	35.0 abcd	IET17327	14.0 bcdefghij
Vaigai	34.3 abcde	PTB10	13.3 cdefghij
Karuna	31.3 abcdef	IET6101	13.3 cdefghij
IET6579	31.0 abcdef	IET7012	12.5 cdefghij
Chandrikar	29.7 abcdefg	IET7236	9.1 cdefghij
IET7328	28.8 abcdefgh	IET7013	8.1 cdefghij
IET7174	28.8 abcdefgh	IET6109	6.9 efghij
IET6296	28.2 abcdefghi	IET6 266	6.6 efghij
Bhavani	26.5 abcdefghij	IET6 727	4.9 fghij
Jaya	25.8 abcdefghij	IET7014	4.6 fghij
IET6730	25.2 abcdefghij	IET6293	2.7 ghij
Puduvai Ponni	24.8 abcdefghij	IET6286	1.3 hij
IR8	23.6 abcdefghij	IET7015	0.6 ij
Kakatiya	23.1 abcdefghij	Vikram	0.6 ij
IET6080	22.1 abcdefghij	IET7010	0.0 j
PTB21	21.8 abcdefghij	Phalguna	0.0 j
MDU-1	19.7 abcdefghij	IET7016	0.0 j
Kuruvai	17.4 bcdefghij	IET6290	0.0 j
IET6757	17.1 bcdefghij	IET7009	0.0 j
IET7026	16.5 bcdefghij	IET7008	0.0 j
CV (%) = 81.27		F value = 2.56** at 1% level.	

^aAv of 3 replications. ^bMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 1% level.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Hybrid rice

Isolation of maintainers and restorers for Chinese male-sterile lines

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Following successful development of cytoplasmic genetic male-sterile lines in China, heterosis breeding of rice became a commercial reality. We sought to identify effective, stable restorers for the Chinese cytoplasmic genetic male-sterile lines Zhen Shan 97A, Er Jiu Nan 1A, and V20A. We evaluated many crosses, in-

Table 1. List of complete restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers identified at Delhi and Aduthurai, India, for Chinese cytoplasmic genetic male-sterile lines, 1982.

Male-sterile line	Complete restorers (R)	Partial restorers (PR)	Maintainers (M)
	<i>Delhi (kharif)</i>		
Zhen Shan 97A	Pusa 245-51-1 Pusa 212 IR26 IR36 IR9761-19-1 IR19793-25-2-2-2 IET4141 Mijingem	TKM6 ADT33 IR9782-111-2-1-2 Pak Bas 177 Gharbharan Ratna Saket 4	Pusa 3 12 Pusa 150-21-1 ITA225 ITA 119 ITA118 ITA 141 ITA117 ITA175 ITA116 AC5725 Bas 370 Type 3 Karnal Local

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